

A New method for image encryption based on 2D-3D Chaotic Maps

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Abstract- Using the chaotic theory in the color image encryption become a popular research field in recent decades. This paper suggests a color image encryption method based on combines between 3D-Logistic maps and 2D Cat Mapping. This method depends on splitting the original color image in to three essential components Red, Green and Blue in the first stage and then using 3D-Logistic maps to generate random numbers to encrypt the information of image through generating three keys one for each essential color in the second stage. using the 2D Cat Mapping to generate random numbers to scramble the pixels in the image that got from previous step . After applying the proposed method, we obtain an image that has two levels of protection (encryption and rearranging the locations of the image pixels).

Keywords- Chaotic Map; 3D-Logistic maps; 2D Cat Mapping; Image encryption

I. INTRODUCTION

In the recent decades highly growth of multimedia and digital image technology, Therefore, the protection of digital images has become very important, especially during transmission over networks and the Internet. Encrypting image information is one of the methods that protect this information[1].

The traditional methods used in encryption such as DES, AES and IDEA are no longer a suitable option for encryption the image, as the image contains some characteristics such as high correlation, enormous data, bulk data capacity and long redundancy, that distinguish it from the textual content[2, 3]. A solution to the problem of inherent properties in the image was found by introducing a new system based on chaos, this system has some characteristics such as (randomness, sensitivity to initial condition, determinism, and because of these characteristics make chaos common in the domain of image encryption [4]. Engineering, mathematics ,

biology , physics and so on. in 1963 the chaotic process was first described by Lorenz, who developed a system that was coupled to nonlinear differential equations called the Lorenz attractor [5]. A number of researchers have proposed image encryption systems based on chaotic maps in the last years, Several of these systems have also been successfully developed [6].

II. MULTIDIMENSIONAL CHAOTIC FUNCTIONS

A. Cat Mapping:

Arnold was the first one that introduce the 2D cat map in the research periodic theory. Let a 2D Cat map with two positive control parameters and the coordinates of positions of pixels in the original image are $q = \{(x1, y1) \mid x1, y1 = 1, 2, 3, \dots, P\}$, is as follows:

$$x1' = (x1 + my1) \bmod(P) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$y1' = (nx1 + (mb+1)y1) \bmod(P) \dots\dots(2)$$

Where

$(x1, y1)$ = the position of pixels in the original image.

$(x1', y1')$ = the new position of the pixels when applying the cat map once time

m & n = positive number represent control parameter,

P = represent the width or height of the original image.

cat map used to rearrange all the pixels position in the original image ,so old position $(x1,y1)$ are replaced with new position $(x1',y1')$. The image appears without meaning and distorted after many times of iterations because the correlation among the adjacent pixels are distorted. The original image will be return when iterating the work many times, the cat

map is periodic. To resolve the periodic problem for the cat map, generate parameters (m, n) at random by used the 2D Zaslavskii map. [4].

B. 3D Logistic Map :

As logistic map is considered as the most simplest chaotic function so it's defined by the equation

$$X_{n+1} = \lambda X_n(1 - X_n) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

The equation shows chaotic behavior when $0 < X_n < 1$ and $\lambda = 4$. Here a 3 dimensional logistic map is used. The equations are as follows:

$$x_{i+1} = \lambda x_i (1 - x_i) + \beta y_i^2 x_i + \alpha z_i^3 \dots (4)$$

$$y_{i+1} = \lambda y_i (1 - y_i) + \beta z_i^2 y_i + \alpha x_i^3 \dots (5)$$

$$z_{i+1} = \lambda z_i (1 - z_i) + \beta x_i^2 z_i + \alpha y_i^3 \dots (6)$$

The above exhibits equations have good chaotic characteristics when $3.53 < \lambda < 3.81$, $0 < \beta < 0.022$, $0 < \alpha < 0.015$ and it takes the values between [0, 1]. [5,8,9].

III. RELATED WORK

Salah T. A., May M. A., Reyadh H. M. [10] Proposed a new way to encrypt image by combining 2D Cat Mapping and 1D-Logistic maps. Where 1D-Logistic map was used in order to generate three keys use in the stage of encryption the image data, and 2D Cat Mapping was also used to generate random numbers to be used in the stage of rearranging the locations of pixels in the image.

Md.Billal H., Md.Toufikur R., A B M Saadmaan R., Sayeed I. [11] proposed a method based on non-linear 3D chaos to execute simple encryption way. in this way used the 3D chaos for position reordering and value converted technique.

Chunhu Li, Guangchun Luo, and Chunbao Li [5] proposed a new method to encryption image depending on 3D chaotic logistic map.

- 1- generate a key stream through modified the 3D chaotic logistic map.
- 2- using the 3D chaotic logistic map to generate the chaos-based key stream, which have better performance in terms of security level and randomness properties.

IV. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

A. Encryption System

The outline for the suggested method is shown in fig.1 . this method have two levels of the security, the first one is the image encryption and the second is pixel permutation for the image encrypted.

1. Encrypted image

This stage include read color image, divided this image into the essential components color Red, Green, and Blue, generate 3 keys (KR, BG, KB) by using 3D Logistic maps and then perform the encryption process through doing the XOR operation between the values of each color with their respective key values .

Figure 1. The general outline of Encryption Stage

The main steps below illustrate algorithm of image encryption:

- 1: Read color image (M) .
- 2 : Split the image (M) into essential components R ,G, B.
- 3: Convert the color value for each component to 1D array (MR, MG, MB).
- 4: Generate 3 keys (KR, KG, KB) by using 3D Logistic maps
- 5: Encrypted (MR , MG, MB) with the respective key (KR, KG, KB)
- 6: Convert the result of the previous step for each component to 2D array.
- 7: The result of this stage is encrypted image (IE) .

2. *Permutation pixels*

Permutation stage include generate a key consist of a random numbers through using 2D cat mapping. this key using to rearranging the positions of the all pixels in the image

The main steps below illustrate algorithm of Permutation pixels:

- 1: Generate key (NK) by using 2D cat maps consist of random numbers.
- 2: Using the key (NK) to rearrange the pixels position for the encrypted image (IE).
- 3: The result of applying the suggested method is to get out an encrypted image with rearrange the pixels positions (IEP)

B. *Decryption System*

This stage include reverse all operation that applying in the encryption stage. First step includes entering the encrypted image, second step includes using 2D Cat Mapping to Regenerate the same key to Recover the original location for the pixels in the encrypted image, third step includes Recover the original image through using the 3D Logistic maps and the same initial numbers to regenerate the three mask keys (Kr, Kg, Kb) to decrypted the image . Fig.2. illustrate the outline for the decrypted stage.

Figure 2 The general outline of decryption Stage

V. PROPOSED METHODES TEST

The proposed method, used color Lena image as the test image. The color image entering to the propose method is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3 original Lena image

The 3D logistic Map method was used in the encryption stage. The result image after applying encryption stage is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Lena image encrypted

The 2D logistic Map method was used in the permutation stage. The result image after applying this stage is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5 Result image

A. *Histogram*

The statistical properties of the image are determined by finding the histogram of the image data. Therefore, in the proposed method, these properties are canceled and the data are made to appear unified to protect it from statistical attacks. Fig. 6, 7 and 8 shown the histogram for the essential components Red, Green and Blue before and after applying the proposed method..

Figure 6. (a- Red color before encryption
b- red color after encryption)

Figure 7. (a- Green color before encryption
b- Green color after encryption)

Figure 8. (a- Blue color before encryption
b- Blue color after encryption)

B. NPCR & UACI

To calculate the value of (NPCR) between the pixels of the encrypted image and the plain image used the eq. 7 and 8 [5]:

$$NPCR = \frac{\sum_{i,j} R(i,j)}{N * M} * 100 \dots \dots (7)$$

$$R(i,j) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } B_1(i,j) = B_2(i,j) \\ 1, & \text{if } B_1(i,j) \neq B_2(i,j) \end{cases} \dots \dots (8)$$

To calculate the value of (UACI) between the encrypted and plain image used the eq.9 [5]

$$UACI = \sum \frac{|B_1(i,j) - B_2(i,j)|}{255} * 100 \dots \dots (9)$$

Table (1) shows a comparison between the value of (NPCR) of the proposed method and other methods

TABLE 1. Shows the comparison in value of NPCR

Encryption Method	NPCR
Proposed Method	99.64
Ref. [2]	99.62
Ref. [3]	99.61

Table (2) shows a comparison between the value of (UACI) of the proposed method and other methods

TABLE 2. Shows the comparison in value of UACI

Encryption Method	UACI
Proposed Method	30.66
Ref. [2]	33.39
Ref. [3]	33.49

C. Entropy

To calculate the entropy to the system, used the eq.10 [5].

$$H(q) = - \sum_{i=0}^{255} p(q_i) \log_2 p(q_i) \dots \dots (10)$$

Where: p(q_i) The probability of (q_i), and the entropy is represented by bits. When the value of the entropy is close to the value (8) of the encrypted image it is better. Table (3) shows a difference between the value of entropy for the proposed method and other methods.

TABLE 3. Showing the difference of Entropy value

Encryption Method	red
Proposed Method	7.998
Ref. [2]	7.997
Ref. [3]	7.997

VI. CONCLUSION

The proposed method consists of two levels of protection as it relies on chaotic maps. The 3D logistic maps were used in the image encryption process, which represents the first level of protection. As for the 2D cat mapping, they were used in the process of rearranging the locations of the image pixels, and this represents the second level of protection. A number of statistical methods have been tried on the encrypted image such as (NPCR, UACI, Entropy), As the proposed method has proven efficient and When using the histogram of the encrypted image, a uniformly distributed was shown

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